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Complexity for heterogeneous classes: teaching embedded systems using an open project approach

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ABSTRACT

Modern embedded systems are a complex mixture of hardware and software components, like for Internet of Things and Industry 4.0 applications. The technical challenges when teaching embedded systems include the basic hardware like microcontrollers, low-level software development as well as more sophisticated high-level software stacks and modules and finally complex applications. On the other hand the previous knowledge of course participants in master degree programs often differ drastically, from absolute beginners to rather experienced developers of embedded systems. Taking the technical and the non-technical challenges into account this paper presents an open project approach for heterogeneous classes taking an embedded systems course as an example. To enable an individual learning success for all participants it combines elements of typical lectures with elements of flipped classroom and project-based learning (PBL). One part of the course uses standard lectures to get every student to a defined knowledge level. In the other part students define their own projects based on a complex microcontroller system according to their prerequisites and individual focus areas. Additional teaching material is provided online for the students that can be selected according to the needs of the project. This open project approach strengthens the benefits of learning techniques like PBL and flipped classroom, increases the self-motivation of the students and encourages the students significantly to work on the project and to gain hands-on experience in developing embedded systems. The combination of modern teaching techniques with the open project is suitable for other subjects as well.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Teaching heterogeneous classes is rather challenging and many different teaching strategies were developed with different emphasis on problem or project based learning, online and offline activities or active learning [1, 2]. The heterogeneity may be caused by different kinds of learners, different social or educational background, different mother languages, different previous knowledge and interests. For the course Electronics for Automatization, which is the base for this paper, in particular the heterogeneity with regard to different previous knowledge and the interests are the main challenges.

Problem or project based learning (both abbreviated with PBL) or cooperative learning are commonly used methods for teaching heterogeneous classes, in particular to increase the hands-on experiences and practical abilities of the students [3, 4, 5, 6]. These methods target to motivate the students to be engaged with the material, show interest in the course contents, participate in the class and collaborate with other students.

With regard to electrical engineering PBL is commonly used, both for complete curricula like in [7] or for dedicated courses. In [8] and [4] the PBL approach is described for courses in embedded systems. They are based on field-programmable gate arrays (FPGA) and microcontrollers respectively and use fixed projects for the lab work. Whereas problem based learning approaches define a specific problem to be solved by the students, project based learning relies more on self-defined projects of the students. The current work presented in this paper combines a conventional lecture style with a new approach for the project based methods for the lab. This new approach is based on the self-motivation of the students and the finding that the motivation is highest if the students can work on their own ideas and projects.

2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The course Electronics for Automatization is part of the curriculum of the master program Electrical Engineering at UAS Aachen [9]. Main topic of this course is teaching embedded systems and in particular microcontroller systems. The course consists of lecture (2 lessons per week), exercise (2 lessons per week) and lab with just a one lesson per week. The class is always rather heterogeneous with up to 40 students participating in this one-term-course of the master program every year. About 25 % of the students have passed their bachelor at other universities, roughly half of these at foreign universities (e.g. from India, China or Mexico). For the foreign students also the language is sometimes a problem as the course is in German. About 20 % of the participants finished their bachelor in other departments of UAS Aachen, e.g. Mechanical Engineering and Mechatronics. Even the students from Electrical Engineering department have chosen different focus areas during their bachelor. Therefore the previous knowledge of the students is very different. Some students never experienced anything with embedded systems, some already attended classes on this subject and yet others have a rather big know-how due to

intensive work with embedded systems during their bachelor thesis or student jobs. In addition the interests of the students differ significantly.

This diversity in knowledge and interests is one part of the challenges during the embedded systems course. The other big challenge is the complexity of modern embedded systems that combine sophisticated hardware (HW) with several different software parts (SW), from low-level drivers to high-level application software. As most embedded systems use microcontrollers as the central device these Integrated Circuits (IC) are the major subject of the course. To cover all aspects of the development of microcontroller based embedded systems state-of-the-art microcontrollers and development environments are used, both for the lecture as well as for the lab. Initially using Renesas' RL78 16-bit microcontrollers the course switched to 32-bit microcontrollers of Renesas' Synergy platform that was launched just some years ago. The Synergy platform fits perfectly into the teaching goals of the course as it enables system development at very different levels – from just simple applications to highly-sophisticated networking and IoT (Internet of Things) applications.

Finally the goal of the course is rather simple: every student should have at least the basic theoretical background of embedded systems and microcontroller systems and in addition should gain hands-on experience with embedded systems no matter of his individual prerequisites. These goals mean that there has to be some overall theoretical part which is the same for all students and each student should be encouraged to develop his own skills further, independently of the abilities of the other students. To motivate everyone to work for the second goal the lab is setup rather individually in small groups like described below.

3 TECHNICAL CONTENT OF THE COURSE

The course is based on state-of-the-art microcontrollers from Renesas Electronics as these microcontrollers are commonly used in many different industries, from automation systems to consumer, automotive and medical applications. The microcontrollers are rather complex and provide all hardware features that are used in modern applications like IoT or Industry 4.0 applications. Initially the 16-bit RL78 microcontroller was used for the course. Besides the hardware of the microcontroller a dedicated integrated development environment (IDE, e2studio which is based on Eclipse) and additional tools like Applilet, a graphical configuration tool for the basic setup of the microcontroller, is provided as well. After the launch of the Renesas Synergy Platform the course switched to the Synergy S7G2 microcontroller [10]. This platform provides a complete ecosystem for the development of advanced applications in all fields of interest. Besides the sophisticated hardware, here the 32-bit S7G2 microcontroller with an ARM architecture, the ecosystem consists of powerful development, software and application packages. The IDE is again the eclipse based e2studio, but this time powerful software packages to simplify the configuration and programming are already implemented:

- Board Support Package (BSP) for graphical configuration
- Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL) for direct programming of the hardware modules
- Real-Time Operating System
- Functional libraries, application frameworks and middleware for high level programming
- Connectivity modules

Taking all these features into account the Renesas Synergy platform provides everything that is needed to teach the development of modern microcontroller based embedded systems. Furthermore it allows to start with just the basic features to realize simple applications as well as the use of the complex features to develop more complex applications – again individually fitting to the prerequisites of the students.

4 CONCEPT AND REALIZATION

To reach the two goals defined above – at least same theoretical background for all students and individual enhancement of practical skills – the teaching methods for the lecture and the lab part are set up in a different way.

The lecture is conducted in a rather conventional way and starts with the introduction to embedded systems and microcontrollers at the very beginning to provide the basis for the following topics. Based on these fundamentals and on some basic programming skills software architectures and methods are introduced, like middleware and real-time operating systems (RTOS). These topics build the minimum knowledge every student should acquire during the lecture. The example systems used during the lecture are the same like the systems used during the lab. For more advanced students additional material is provided in a kind of flipped classroom approach. This material contains more detailed and comprehensive information about sophisticated topics like hardware abstraction layer (HAL), RTOS, application frameworks and connectivity. Using this additional material each student can individually select the complexity and topic that fits to both his previous knowledge and lab project.

The lab is set up in a collaborative learning style with an open project for each group of students. The formation of the groups isn't done by the lecturer but by the students. Therefore some of the groups are more homogeneous than others. According to [11] open project approach means that each group of one to four students define their very own project based on the microcontroller platform introduced in the lecture. In addition it is possible for the groups to order additional equipment if needed for the project, e.g. hardware extensions, additional components or other material. After the project was defined the groups make a timeline for their projects and directly start working on the projects right from the beginning of the course. This work includes everything from the basic setup of the systems and development environment to the hardware parts and the programming

of the software including low-level drivers, RTOS and application software. The work is done more or less absolutely on their own. During official lab times there is the chance for getting support and help in case of severe problems, but in general the students are encouraged to solve all issues and problems on their own or within the group. The work is supported by dedicated teaching material like data sheets, a course book and slides covering everything that is needed. Even though this approach might cause some frustration and delays, in particular in the practical work, it prepares the students for working as an engineer finally.

At the end of the course each group prepares a final presentation of their work and project, including drawback, problems, pros and cons. As there is no final grading of the projects this approach strongly relies on the self-motivation, interest and trustworthiness of the students to realize an own project within a group. This point will be evaluated in detail below.

5 EVALUATION

The evaluation of the course and the free work approach is done in three steps:

- Standard evaluation of the course
- Review of projects developed during the free lab
- Personal feedback

At UAS Aachen each course is evaluated by a standardized evaluation process each year [12]. The evaluation is done at the end of the lecture period but before the exam. The feedback of the students is anonym and contains many questions about the content of the course, the learning atmosphere, the workload and many more. During the last five years about 160 students attended the course and the average rating on a scale from 1 (best) to 5 (worst) reveals a 1.3, for the single years ranging from 1.1 to 1.5. After the winter term 2017/2018 an additional question was added to the evaluation form: ‘In my opinion, the supervision of the practical course suited my educational needs’. The answers to this question answered by 20 students revealed an average of 2.1 (1: fully agree, 5: fully disagree) (*Table 1*).

Table 1. Student feedback to the question ‘In my opinion, the supervision of the practical course suited my educational needs’ on a scale from 1 (fully agree) to 5 (fully disagree)

Evaluation	1	2	3	4	5
Number of answers	7	8	2	1	2

Another question of the official evaluation is related to the additional workload the students spend. For this course the additional workload is mainly due to the free project work and hence is a measure for the commitment of the students to their work. The official time for the lab is just one lesson per week (45 minutes). In average the students spend about 3 additional hours for the lab which means four

times the originally planned time of one lesson. Here the range is from 0 hours to more than 7 hours per week.

The last item of the official evaluation form is a free text field where the students can provide their personal feedback. Regarding the lab there were some comments very common during the 5 years, both positive and negative (*Table 2*).

Table 2. Common comments of the official evaluation

Pros	Cons
Free project without constraints	Missing introduction to lab work
High motivation of the students	Too complex microcontroller system
Incorporation of own ideas	No final grading

Looking at the projects that were realized during the last five years it becomes obvious that the projects cover the complete range from very simple to rather complex applications like shown in the examples listed in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Examples for projects developed during the free lab, evaluation by lecturer and co-workers

Project	HW complexity	SW complexity	Previous knowledge
LED control by external buttons	Low	Low	Low
Control of a 4x4x4 LED cube	Low	Medium	Low
Radio controlled clock using the DCF77 signal	Low	Medium	Medium
Sensor cluster	Medium	Low	Medium
Sensor cluster with TCP/IP connection and LabView	High	High	High
Spaceflight video game using external acceleration sensors and a display	High	High	High

Last but not least the personal feedback of the students is taken into account. This feedback is given verbally during the course and also after the course and the exams. Therefore this feedback can hardly be quantified but is a rather subjective

value. The feedback is very often positive, similar to the comments of the official evaluation. In particular the possibility to work on their own without any pressure is highly appreciated by most students. They also confirm that their learning curve is high and independent of the previous knowledge. Major drawback is the starting phase of the project, i.e. the initial installation and setup of the development environment and the first step with the new system.

6 DISCUSSION

The results of the evaluation clearly reveal the pros and cons of the open project approach from student point of view. These items of the students can be matched to the expectations and assessment of the course instructor as depicted in *Table 4*.

The main positive points of the students are the freedom during the project work and the motivation to work on own projects. From instructor point of view these points are also reflected by the additional workload the students spent and the projects that were realized. Each group during the last five years finalize their project, no matter of the previous knowledge or the complexity of the project or the time they needed.

Main negative feedbacks by some students were the missing supervision of the projects, in particular in the initial phase, the complexity of the microcontroller systems and the missing grading of the project work. These feedbacks were expected by the instructor as they are related to the basic setup and approach of the course. The missing direct supervision is one of the concepts of the course. Everything they need for the project work is provided, but the students have to acquire everything they need for the realization on their own. This approach intends to prepare the students for their engineering work in their future working life – get information, extract the relevant and needed information and get the work done on your own. This approach is also related to the second drawback, the complexity of the microcontroller system some students stated. Again, using an industrial state-of-the-art system is the best preparation for real engineering life. Finally the missing final grade for the project – in particular stated by some of the students that realized really complex projects like the Spaceflight video game – was one complaint. But the missing grading is a key point to enable fully free and open project work for the students.

Table 4. Main feedback of the students compared to the expectations and assessment of the instructor

Feedback item	Judgement by students	Instructor's expectation	Instructor's assessment
Freedom of project work	+	Met	+: all projects were finalized
Own project	+	Met	+: large variety of projects of different

			complexity levels
Motivation	+	Met	+: high additional workload, range of complexity
Supervision of project work	Mainly +, some -	Met	+: goal of the course: find own solutions and get system running on their own, good preparation for engineering work
Complexity of microcontroller	Mainly +, some -	Mostly met	+: good preparation for industrial work as an engineer -: some students have to fight hard with the microcontroller
No final grading	Mainly +, some -	Met	+: no grading enables fully free and open work on the projects without pressure

7 SUMMARY

The open project approach is well established within the master course Electronics for Automatization at UAS Aachen. Open projects means that the students define and work on their own projects during the lab of the course. There are no restrictions regarding the size or complexity of the projects and the students are encouraged to define the projects according to their previous knowledge and interests. To avoid any external pressure there is no final grading of the projects. A rather conventional lecture about the basic theory of embedded systems supports the project work.

After five years the open project approach is evaluated by official evaluation, direct feedback by the students and a review of the projects that were realized. This evaluation reveals the major pros and cons of this approach and is matched to the instructor's expectations. Most of the feedback highly appreciates the chance to work in a free manner on an open and self-defined project. The major negative aspects of the students are clearly related to the basic concept of open projects and hence is judged to be rather fitting.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Fitzgerald, E., Lentmaier, M. (2016), Strategies for Teaching Students with Heterogeneous Prior Knowledge, *LTHs 9:e Pedagogiska Inspirationskonferens, 15 december 2016*.
- [2] Aluvalu, R., Kulkarni, V., Asif, M. (2017), Handling Classrooms with Students having Heterogeneous Learning Abilities, *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*, Volume 30, No. 3, pp 229 - 234.
- [3] Fedorinova, Z. V., Pozdeeva, S. I., Solonenko, A. V. (2018), Collaborative Learning in Engineering Education: Reaching New Quality and Outcomes, *Linguistic and Cultural Studies: Traditions and Innovations, Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing 677*, A. Filchenko and Z. Anikina, pp 10 - 18.
- [4] Prasad, M. R., Reddy, D. K. (2015), Project Based Teaching Methodology for Embedded Engineering Education, *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*, Special Issue: Jan. 2015, pp 52 – 57.
- [5] Fernandez, M. (2017), Project-based learning applied to an embedded systems course, *IJEEE*, Vol. 54, No. 3, pp 223 – 235.
- [6] Johnson, M., Hayes, M. J. (2016), A comparison of problem-based and didactic learning pedagogies on an electronics engineering course, *IJEEE*, Vol. 53, No. 1, pp 3 – 22.
- [7] Macías-Guarasa, J., Montero, J. M., San-Segundo, R., Araujo, Á, Nieto-Taladriz, O. (2016), A Project-Based Learning Approach to Design Electronic Systems Curricula, *IEEE Transactions on education*, Vol. 49, No. 3, Pp 389 – 397.

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- [8] Kumar, A., Fernando, S., Panicker, R.C. (2013), Project-Based Learning in Embedded Systems Education Using an FPGA Platform, *IEEE Transactions on education*, Vol. 56, No. 4, pp 407 – 415.
- [9] <https://www.fh-aachen.de/studium/elektrotechnik-meng/studieninhalte/> (last access October 2018)
- [10] <https://www.renesas.com/kr/en/products/synergy.html> (last access October 2018).
- [11] Cigdemoglu, C., Kapusuz, K.Y., Kara, A. (2014), Heterogeneity in Classes: Cooperative Problem-Solving Activities through Cooperative Learning, *Croatian Journal of Education*, Vol.16, No.4, pp 999 – 1029.
- [12] <https://www.fh-aachen.de/en/university/zentrum-fuer-hochschuldidaktik-und-qualitaetsentwicklung-zhq/aufgaben-service/evaluation/lehrveranstaltungsevaluation/> (last access October 2018).